

Friedel-Crafts Chemistry. XXI. Cyclisation versus Elimination Behaviour of some 1-Naphthyl-containing Carbinols under the Influence of Acid Catalysts

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Friedel-Crafts cyclisation reactions (cyclialkylations and cycliacylations) have been at the heart of several approaches to ring-forming methodologies. Over the years, an astonishing array of intriguing polycyclic compounds and even cage structures have been synthesised through various modifications¹. Inspired by our continuing interest in cyclialkylations^{1b,2,3} and by the developing industrial and biological importance of acenaphthene derivatives⁴, we have undertaken a research project aiming at their synthesis by this methodology. In two recent publications^{2,3}, we described some facile methods for the synthesis of 1,1-dimethyl- and 1,1,2-trimethylacenaphthenes through direct (e.g. 1→4) and rearranged (e.g. 2 or 3→4) cyclialkylation reactions (Scheme 1).

Results and Discussion

The reactions of carbinols 5-9 with 85-90% H₂SO₄, PPA an/or AlCl₃/CH₃NO₂ was explored to find out whether or not cyclialkylation to acenaphthene and/or hydrophenalene derivatives would take place. For clarity and simplicity, the results and discussion are presented below under specified subheadings.

1-(1-Naphthyl)-2-phenylethanol (5): Treatment of this carbinol with either 85% H₂SO₄ or AlCl₃/CH₃NO₂ catalyst did not result in any cyclialkylation to 1-phenyl-acenaphthene (10). This conclusion was based on a comparison of the ¹H nmr spectra of the products with that reported⁵ for 10. The failure of this ring closure could be attributed to one or more of several factors: (a) the need for prior carbocation rearrangement from C₁ where the OH rests to benzylic C₂ where the closure site is to be expected, (b) 2° benzylic carbocations are generally sluggish in their ring closure behaviour regardless of ring size⁶⁻⁸, (c) the developing steric interactions between the bulky phenyl group and the *peri* hydrogen undoubtedly add to the difficulty of this closure, and finally (d) styrenes and systems leading to them (by dehydration or dehydrohalogenation) are prone to di- and/or polymerise under the influence of

acid catalysis^{1a,b}. However, since our main goal was centered on ring closure we did not bother to identify the product(s).

	X	R ¹	R ²		R ¹	R ²	R ³	R ⁴
5;	Bond	H	CH ₂ Ph	10,	Ph	H	H	H
6;	Bond	Ph	CH ₂ Ph	11,	Ph	Ph	H	H
7;	CH ₂	Ph	Ph	12,	Ph	H	Ph	H
8;	(CH ₂) ₂	Me	Me					
9;	(CH ₂) ₂	Ph	Ph					

16

17

	R ¹	R ²	R ³
13,	Ph	Ph	H
14,	H	Ph	Ph
15,	H	Ph	CH ₂ Ph

18

1-(1-Naphthyl)-1,2-diphenylethanol (6): Treatment of carbinol 6 with either 85% H₂SO₄, PPA or NaHSO₄ catalyst gave stereoisomeric mixture 13 with *E*-isomer predominating due to decreased steric hindrance. Attempts to effect the cyclialkylation of 6 were extended to include catalysis by AlCl₃/CH₃NO₂. Again, no cyclisation took place but a polymeric material resulted in which no more than 2% of the *E*- and *Z*-isomers of 13 were present (glpc). The failure of 6 to cyclialkylate to 1,2-diphenylacenaphthene can very well be attributed to factors similar to those suggested for the parallel behaviour of carbinol 5.

2-(1-Naphthyl)-1,1-diphenylethanol (7): Earlier, we found³ that the reaction of 7 with 85-95% H₂SO₄, PPA, H₂SO₄/CH₃COOH or NaHSO₄ resulted exclusively in elimination to 14 with no sign of cyclialkylation to 11

Hoping to effect cyclialkylation of 7 we induced its re-

action by $\text{AlCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ catalyst. The product, which seemed to be somewhat different from that with previous catalyst, was subjected to chromatographic and spectroscopic investigations. While tlc revealed the presence of at least four components in the crude, column chromatography led to separation into a major fraction composed almost totally of 1-(1-naphthyl)-2,2-diphenylethene (**14**), a minor fraction believed to consist mainly of 1,1-diphenylacenaphthene (**11**) together with little of *trans*-1,2-diphenylacenaphthene (**12**) and a higher molecular weight fraction which could not be characterised. Although no direct experimental evidence is presently available, support for the presence of **11** and **12** is based on two justifications: (i) GC/MS gave a molecular ion base peak at m/z 306 confirming a molecular formula of $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{18}$ and (ii) ^1H nmr showed two distinct aliphatic singlets at δ 3.56 and 4.71 besides an aromatic multiplet at δ 6.90–8.24. With reference to literature data^{5,9}, these nmr signals are best accommodated by assignment to **11** and **12** respectively.

2-Methyl-4-(1-naphthyl)-2-butanol (8): Treatment of this carbinol with either 85% H_2SO_4 or $\text{AlCl}_3\text{-CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ catalyst gave products, the elemental, spectral and chromatographic data of which were consistent with a mixture of the cyclialkylation isomers 1,1-dimethyldihydrophenalene (**16**; 83%) and 1,1-dimethyl-2,3-dihydrobenz[e]indene (**17**; 17%). The distinction between isomers **16** and **17** was based on three substantiated assumptions: (i) six-membered ring formation is usually favoured over five-membered ring^{1b,11,12}, (ii) electrophilic attack at the α -position of naphthalene is energetically favoured over β -attack and (iii) the methylene protons in six-membered dihydrophenalene are expectedly more shielded than in five-membered hydrindene¹³. In practice, we found this to be the case. An ^1H nmr spectrum of the product showed two pairs of triplets: a major one at δ 1.83 and 3.13 for protons *b* and *a* of dihydrophenalene **16** and a minor one at δ 2.05 and 3.18 for protons *d* and *c* of **17** respectively. Notably, the latter triplet was mostly overlapped by that of protons *a* of **16**.

3-(1-Naphthyl)-1,1-diphenylpropanol (9): The closure of this carbinol was attempted with H_2SO_4 , PPA and $\text{AlCl}_3\text{-CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ catalysts but all attempts were met with failure. While treatment with H_2SO_4 resulted in direct elimination to 3-(1-naphthyl)-1,1-diphenyl-1-propene (**18**), that with $\text{AlCl}_3\text{-CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ yielded **15**, the stereochemistry around its olefinic bond being not ascertained. The treatment of carbinol **9** with PPA gave a more complex product mixture consisting of **15** beside new components whose identity have not yet been disclosed. Notably, a product of similar nature also resulted in two other reactions: (i) upon treatment of carbinol **9** with $\text{AlCl}_3\text{-CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ at 60° for 2 h and (ii) upon recycling of the proposed **15** product with a new patch of $\text{AlCl}_3\text{-CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ catalyst in petroleum ether solvent at room temperature for 2 h.

In concluding this discussion we like to point out that the reaction outcome for the acid-catalysed treatment of carbinols **5–9** is highly dependent not only on experimental conditions but also on carbocation stabilities and steric interactions. Under the employed conditions the following points can be emphasised: (i) carbinols **5** and **6** failed to undergo rearranged cyclialkylations to acenaphthenes, undergoing instead ordinary eliminations to alkene(s), (ii) carbinols of general formula $1\text{-C}_{10}\text{H}_7(\text{CH}_2)_{1,2}\text{C}(\text{OH})\text{R}_2$ manifested considerable dependence of ring closure facility on steric factors; whereas diphenyl carbinols **7** and **9** failed to cyclise leading only to olefins, dimethyl carbinols **1** and **8** underwent facile closure to 5- and/or 6-membered rings and (iii) with reference to the same general formula, cyclialkylation versus elimination was found to vary with R size like this:

Experimental

Most instrumental techniques and analytical instruments were the same as described^{2,3} previously. Unless otherwise specified, ^1H nmr spectra were recorded at 90 MHz in CCl_4 solution, chemical shifts being measured downfield of internal tetramethylsilane. GC/MS data were recorded in the electron-impact (EI) mode (70 eV). Unless otherwise specified, column chromatographic purifications were carried out with silica gel (Fluka AG, 35–70 mesh) using the indicated eluents. Analytical tlc was performed using aluminium cards precoated with silica gel (0.2 mm) having fluorescent indicator, 254 nm (Fluka) and visualisation was done either by irradiation with a Black-Ray UVL-21 lamp (Ultra Violet Products Inc.) or by exposure to iodine vapour. Yields and product composition refer to chromatographically and spectroscopically homogeneous materials. Chemicals were of commercial grade and unless specified otherwise, were used as such. Ether used for Grignard reactions was dried over sodium wire and distilled under dry conditions immediately before use. The organic extracts were dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate.

Synthesis of starting carbinols: The preparation of starting carbinol **7**³ was described previously and others were prepared by the procedures described below.

1-(α -Naphthyl)-2-phenylethanol (5): It was prepared as a white solid by reacting benzylmagnesium iodide with α -naphthaldehyde followed by decomposition with aqueous ammonium chloride, m.p. (crude) 70–72° (Found: C, 88.32; H, 6.64. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$ requires: C, 87.10; H, 6.45); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 200, 3 300 (OH), 1 595 cm^{-1} (aromatic); δ (CCl_4) 2.17 (1H, bs, OH, exchangeable), 2.9–3.1 (2H, m, diastereotopic CH_2), 5.35–5.53 (1H, four-line pattern, chiral CH), 7.0–8.1 (12H, m, ArH).

1-(1-Naphthyl)-1,2-diphenylethanol (6): An ether solution of 1-benzoylnaphthalene¹⁵ (1 mol) was added at room temperature to a stirred ether solution of benzylmagnesium chloride¹⁶ (1 mol) over a period of 30 min. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 30 min and refluxed for 30 more min. The reaction mixture was then decomposed by saturated aqueous NH_4Cl solution and the product extracted with ether. The ethereal extract after usual work-up gave the carbinol 6 as a grey solid (54%), m.p. 142–43° (benzene-pet. ether) (Found: C, 88.68; H, 6.15. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$ calcd. for: C, 88.80; H, 6.17%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 425 cm^{-1} (OH); $^1\text{H nmr } \delta$ (CDCl_3) 2.5 (1H, br s, OH, D_2O exchangeable), 3.7 (ABq with small outer peaks, J 13.5 Hz, diastereotopic CH_2), 6.5–6.7 (2H, m, ArH), 7.0–7.6 (10H, m, ArH), 7.8–8.15 (5H, m, ArH).

2-Methyl-4-(1-naphthyl)-2-butanol (8): Doebner reaction of 1-naphthaldehyde with malonic acid in pyridine solvent and piperidine catalyst followed by decarboxylation¹⁷ gave 3-(1-naphthyl)propenoic acid as white needles from ethanol (78% yield), m.p. 211–13° (lit.¹⁸ 209–12°); ν_{max} (KBr) 2 500–3 100 (group of small bands superimposed on broad OH stretch), 1 681 (C=O), 1 618 cm^{-1} (C=C); $^1\text{H nmr } \delta$ (d_6 -DMSO) 6.58 (1H, d, J 15.2 Hz, =CHCO), 7.40–7.70 (3H, m, ArH), 7.84–8.25 (4H, m, ArH), 8.42 (1H, d, J 15.2 Hz, ArCH=). Esterification of the latter acid with ethanol in the presence of conc. H_2SO_4 catalyst following standard procedure¹⁹ gave ethyl 3-(1-naphthyl)propenoate as viscous yellow liquid²⁰ (85% yield), ν_{max} (neat) 1 728 (C=O), 1 632 cm^{-1} (C=C); $^1\text{H nmr } \delta$ (CDCl_3) 1.10 (3H, t, J 7.5 Hz, CH_3), 4.33 (2H, q, J 7.5 Hz, CH_2), 6.50 (1H, d, J 16.5 Hz, =CHCO), 7.0–8.34 (7H, m, ArH), 8.57 (1H, d, J 16.5 Hz, ArCH=). Reduction of the latter ester with H_2 and Pd/C in ethanol at 60 psi using a Parr low-pressure hydrogenator gave ethyl 3-(1-naphthyl)propanoate in the form of light-yellow oil upon distillation under vacuum (90% yield), b.p. 191–92°/15 mm Hg²¹; ν_{max} (neat) 1 734 (C=O), 1 600 cm^{-1} (C=C aromatic); $^1\text{H nmr } \delta$ (CDCl_3) 1.26 (3H, t, J 7.5 Hz, CH_3), 2.75 (2H, t, J 8.8 Hz, CH_2CO), 3.47 (2H, t, J 8.8 Hz, ArCH_2), 4.2 (2H, q, J 7.5 Hz, OCH_2), 7.30–8.15 (7H, m, ArH). Addition of the latter ester to little over two equivalents of methylmagnesium iodide in dry ether followed by decomposition with saturated aq. NH_4Cl gave the title carbinol 8 as yellowish viscous oil (Found: C, 83.97; H, 8.41. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$ calcd. for: C, 84.11; H, 8.41%); ν_{max} (neat) 3 415 (strong and broad with a shoulder at 3 540) (OH), 1 595 cm^{-1} (C=C aromatic); $^1\text{H nmr } \delta$ (CCl_4) 1.25 (6H, s, 2CH_3), 1.80 (2H, q, $\text{CH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{OH}$), 2.95 (1H, s, OH, D_2O exchangeable), 3.06 (2H, q, ArCH_2), 7.15–7.45 (4H, m, ArH), 7.5–7.85 (2H, m, ArH), 7.85–8.1 (1H, m, ArH).

3-(1-Naphthyl)-1,1-diphenylpropanol (9): Addition of the above-prepared ethyl 3-(1-naphthyl)propanoate to little over two equivalents of phenylmagnesium iodide in dry ether followed by decomposition by saturated aq. NH_4Cl

gave the title carbinol 10 as white needles from pet. ether (b.p. 60–80°) (80% yield), m.p. 118–19° (Found: C, 88.50, H, 6.96. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}$ calcd. for: C, 88.75; H, 6.51%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 528sh (OH), 1 592 cm^{-1} (C=C aromatic); $^1\text{H nmr } \delta$ (CDCl_3) 2.25 (1H, s, OH, D_2O exchangeable), 2.54–3.20 (an AA' BB' multiplet symmetric about 2.87, 4H, ArCH_2CH_2), 7.13–7.93 (17H, m, ArH).

Friedel-Crafts procedure and products: The procedures reported earlier^{2,3,11} for cyclialkylation with AlCl_3 - CH_3NO_2 , H_2SO_4 and PPA were essentially followed using pet. ether (b.p. 60–80°) as solvent with the former two catalysts unless specified otherwise. Generally, all products were purified by column chromatography on silica gel or alumina and were obtained as semisolids or viscous oils. While no more efforts were spent to further purify the products through attempted solidification and/or recrystallisation, they all gave satisfactory elemental data (not recorded for brevity) in accordance with the suggested structures. Other details concerning separation and identification of products from carbinols 5–9 are given below.

Carbinol 5: Attempted cyclialkylations of 5 using 85% H_2SO_4 or AlCl_3 - CH_3NO_2 gave dark gummy products which appeared from spectral and chromatographic analyses to be complex mixtures of elimination and/or polymerisation materials: ν_{max} (KBr) 1 600 cm^{-1} (C=C); $^1\text{H nmr } \delta$ (CDCl_3) 6.33–8.13 (br hump, aromatic). As none of the target 1-phenylacenaphthene (10) could be traced, these products were ignored.

Carbinol 6: Treatment of carbinol 6 with either 85% H_2SO_4 or PPA followed by standard work up resulted in light brown viscous oily crudes whose tlc revealed two spots and glpc showed a mixture of two components. Purification by column chromatography (silica gel, pet. ether) gave a mixture of geometric isomers *E*-13 and *Z*-13 in a 1.8 : 1.0 ratio by glpc. The spectral properties of this mixture were as follows: ν_{max} (neat) 1 660 (C=C), 1 597 cm^{-1} (C=C); $^1\text{H nmr } \delta$ (CDCl_3) 6.84 and 6.93 (1H, 2s, =CH), 6.98–8.30 (17H, m, ArH); GC/MS (EI, 70 eV) m/z (rel. int.) 306 (100, M^+), 289 (20), 276 (7), 228 (49), 215 (16), 151 (10), 144 (10), 77 (2). Further support to isomers *E*-13 and *Z*-13 was gained by comparing their properties with those of a mixture of both isomers prepared authentically by heating carbinol 6 with anhydrous Na_2SO_4 at 160° for 2 h.

Treatment of carbinol 6 with AlCl_3 - CH_3NO_2 followed by column chromatography of the dark oily product (silica gel, pet. ether followed by ether/pet. ether 1 : 1) gave two cuts (83% and 7% based on weight of crude) as brownish viscous oily products. Comparison of spectral and chromatographic data of these products with those of the products from PPA, H_2SO_4 and Na_2SO_4 indicated that the first cut contained about 10% of isomeric *E*- and *Z*-13 with the rest being higher unidentifiable materials giving ions with m/z up to 511. The second minor cut appeared to consist of still higher materials giving ions at m/z up to 573 (50%)

and a base peak at 91. Its ^1H nmr spectrum showed two broad signals at δ 1.2–18 for aliphatic and at 6.0–8.2 for aromatic in a ratio approximating 1 : 10.

Carbinol 7 : Reaction of carbinol 7 with $\text{AlCl}_3\text{-CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ followed by standard work-up gave a dark brown crude amounting to 80% by weight based on starting carbinol. Column chromatography (silica gel, pet. ether followed by ether/pet. ether 1 : 1) gave three distinct cuts. The first and major cut (55% yield, eluted by pet. ether) was shown to be identical in all respects (ir, nmr, GC/MS) with a known³ sample of 13 : GC/MS (EI, 70 eV) m/z (rel. int) 306 (100, M^+), 303 (12), 291 (16), 289 (21), 276 (7), 228 (54), 215 (16), 202 (7), 151 (12), 144 (11), 138 (7), 77(3). The second cut (4%, eluted also by pet. ether) gave an ^1H nmr spectrum showing, amongst other aliphatic and aromatic signals, two aliphatic singlets at δ 3.56 and 4.71 (7 : 1 ratio) which are believed^{5,9} to correspond to 11 and 12 respectively. This was confirmed by MS which showed, among other ions, a peak at m/z 306 corresponding to a molecular formula of $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{18}$.

Carbinol 8 : Reaction of this carbinol with $\text{AlCl}_3\text{-CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ catalyst followed by the usual work-up gave a brownish viscous crude (86%). Purification by column chromatography (silica gel, pet. ether) gave a yellowish oily product mixture (80%) consisting of 16 (83%) and 17 (17%) : ν_{max} (CCl_4) 2 860, 2 937, 2 965, 3 030 (aliphatic and aromatic C–H stretch), 1 597 cm^{-1} (aromatic C=C); ^1H nmr δ (CCl_4) 1.27 (s, *gem*- CH_3 groups of 17), 1.33 (s, *gem*- CH_3 groups of 16), 1.83 (t, protons *b* of 16), 2.05 (t, protons *d* of 26), 3.10 (t, protons *a* of 16), 3.18 (t, protons *c* of 17 overlapped by protons *a* of 16), 7.03–7.70 (m, ArH), (a total aliphatic to aromatic protons ratio of 10 : 6 was observed for the mixture). Treatment of 8 with 85% H_2SO_4 in pet. ether for 3 h at room temperature gave a product similar in nature to that obtained above with $\text{AlCl}_3\text{-CH}_3\text{NO}_2$.

Carbinol 9 : Treatment of carbinol 9 with 85% H_2SO_4 for 2 h at 10–20° followed by column chromatography (alumina, pet. ether) resulted in a yellowish semisolid product, which was found to be alkene 18 : ν_{max} (neat) 1 595 cm^{-1} (C=C); ^1H nmr δ (CCl_4) 3.08 (2H, d, CH_2), 6.18 (1H, t, =CH–), 7.00–7.87 (17H, m, ArH). Treatment of carbinol 9 with $\text{AlCl}_3\text{-CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ in pet. ether solvent for 2 h followed by column chromatography (silica gel, pet. ether) resulted in a yellowish gummy product proposed to be Z-15 : ν_{max} (CCl_4) 2 870–3 810 (C–H stretch), 1 595 cm^{-1} (C=C); ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 2.87 (1H, s, with no sign of allylic coupling, CH_2), 6.63–7.80 (18H, m, vinylic and ArH); GC/MS (EI, 70 eV) m/z (fragment, rel. int.) 320 (M^+ , 63), 243 ($M^+\text{-Ph}$, 67), 229 ($M^+\text{-PhCH}_2$, 10), 65 ($\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_9^+$, 40), 91

(PhCH_2^+ , 100). Treatment of carbinol 9 with $\text{AlCl}_3\text{-CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ catalyst in CH_3NO_2 solvent at 60° for 2 h followed by the standard work-up gave product very similar to the latter one with the exception that ^1H nmr spectra showed two additional broad singlets at δ 1.60 and 4.74 in a 1 : 1 ratio.

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